

ISic1474

I.Sicily inscription 1474

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Helorus

Place of origin (modern)

Eloro

Provenance

In a stretch of the fortification wall

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Eoro, Area archeologica di Eoro

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644984

Bibliography

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